

Advertising Competence (for Personal Care Products) endowed to Consumer Purchase Decisions

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ABSTRACT

Successful multinationals trigger to adopt the strategy of seek first to understand and then to be understood, the same has been centric to the themes of this study that how the corporate houses are capturing the minds of present and future prospects with the aim of value generation with the binding relations to build the advertising competence in their promotional operations. The study involves six independent variables, which best prescribes the measurement parameters for advertising competence and their influential significance on dependent variable of consumer purchase decisions. The objective of the study is to screen out the most contributing variables; whereby a sample of 209 individuals is kept in consideration. The hypothesis regarding six independent variables were formed to evaluate the significant impact on dependent variable; from them four were found accepted and rest of two are rejected for this research. The application of SPSS-18 has been adopted by applying the technique of Linear Regression for data analysis and results interpretation. Thanks to the versatility of the research that it is screened out for three significantly contributing variables in building the advertising competence by boosting their core dimensions, avoiding the rest of others would safeguard resources wastage and promote efficiency in the advertising.

KEYWORDS: Advertising, Competence, Consumer Purchase Decisions, Personal Care Products.

1. INTRODUCTION

Advertising, One of the dimensions of promotional campaign of companies, to be used as increasing the knowledge circle of consumers about, what is being sold in the market, on a particular media. While, the term Competence is central to meaning of proficiency or capability; Competence of a firm is its capability to convey its value generated message to the onboard interested customers to obtain value in return for maximization of communication results (Chizzoli & Pace, 2012); together with advertising it is used to involve that how the media-based communication, is effectively working to influence the Consumer decisions. Advertising influences the decision process (Adhikary, 2014). The Consumer purchase decisions may be tied to the triad of Yes, No or May be situation, to purchase a product, for a particular advertised brand.

The study about competence, in perspectives of advertising industry reveals many of variables to be focused as per the need and enthusiasm of achieving greater and effective influencing results; but here in this research (for personal care products), six sub-variables (four from advertiser side and two from consumer side) are kept in consideration related to advertising competence, to measure its influence level over the consumer purchase decisions, as follows:

Orientation/Consciousness refers to what is the theme point of advertising communication, by participating advertising companies and how they are centric to a direction (as Garnier is proving its brands to be a more careful ideology besides others) or providing the awareness (Unilever's Fair & Lovely focuses on fairness for all and it's Ponds is bonded to CTM: Cleansing, Treating and moisturizing strategy) to consumers to motivate them for the purchase decisions.

Differentiation refers to availability of a broader product range, by width and by depth, because clients make use of different products at different times (Adhikary, 2014). Examples may quote here as Hugo Boss, Lomani, Axe, Fog, Alisha else brings a multi-range in their product line for their brand imagery in market, to broaden consumer choice decisions.

Creativity & Innovation refers to newness (As Unilever is trying to endow Sunsilk product line to co-creations of worldwide renowned fashion houses) and imagination (P&G is about to explore competitive functioning of its Head & Shoulders brand and for Pentene inclines to be the brand of strengthening customized hair care, such as simple, afro/zombie & beehive else) in advertising message.

Cost Criteria suggests that the war is still ahead of all factors, providing a low-cost product line at all (like Lux, Life Boy, Capri, Safeguard, Dettol are always trying to bring style awards, low cost, bundle offers consequently).

Perceived Promotion involves consumer preferences about product promotion, like selection of media, company past record, celebrity endorsement and how the ad is performing its promotional campaign that is pre-identified by consumers.

Behavioral & Psychological issues occupies the competence space in advertising next to perceived promotion, No doubt an ad is placed to improve mind-set of consumers, satisfy and educate them to change their knowledge (Adhikary, 2014) for better choice outcome purchase decisions.

Involving these variable(s), as per the company, customer or market demands (for personal care products), would surely create competence space for product advertising so as to exchange value sharing between two parties; and this is what, ultimately pushes the consumers towards recurring buying decisions for the same, for self and their surroundings.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rajagopal (2006) - The study reveals that 5 Cs (Communication, Caring, Commitment, Comfort and Conflict resolution) of Services marketing play a higher role in cultivating & building brand personality & awareness that are no doubt backed by perceived promotion by customers, when they think that the advertisement is positive to their personality and endorses familiarity attributes in communication message, placed for them. The focus is to form outcomes for long-run branding strategies, involving advertising and variety seeking behavior (behavioral & psychographic).

Hemmatfar, Salehi, & Bayat (2010) - State of information system has been changed, which helps as a fundamental tool to bring about a competitive advantage, Innovation Applications, Process improvement, Partnership Management, Cost Reduction and Strategic Intelligence. The research suggests that the management of the company should focus on pioneer concepts of marketing like value chain that tends to increase profitability, and this is what desired by the Strategic management; The marketers should involve a bundle strategy of focusing multiple factors of information load about each and every factor effecting the business line.

Haque, Rahman, Ahmed, Yasmin, & Asri (2011) - Impact of internet based, commercial and print advertisement is more on consumer choice decisions. The author(s) recommends that if the ad is to provide the consumers with multiple messages to audience, it adds value to consumer decisions. Based on the same, firms can modify their slogans to assist their advertising campaign, and to build consumer loyalty towards a media channel, that finally brings the competence in brand advertisement.

Liu, Lin, & Chen (2011) - It is all about identification of key competencies for an employed individual that must know the science & art of Understanding customer's demand for marketing 4Ps management; Leadership and Communication & coordination for professional efficiency; Initiatives & Observe marketing ethics and law for professional attitude. The same can be the major stand-point for firms to move them from position of simple organization towards learning organization and to bring about a competency in their promotional campaigns with the help of employing best marketing workforce.

Acquisti & Spiekermann (2011) - Consumer attention is a scarce resource for competing firms to obtain via interrupting advertising. Most of consumers would be willing to invest in the brands, whose advertising context might have occupied their memory. Customers were interrupted via controlled advertising in between playing a game and printed on the mugs, they use. Scientifically, it was observed that if an interrupting ad has a primary explanation of features and attributes of a brand, it would create more cognitive learning in consumers mind; and this is how consumer's decisions are being influenced and communication interruptions provide return on investment to the advertising brands.

Goyal & Kumar (2012) - Consumers have multidimensional practical nodes (points) of cross sectional buying decisions and this is what puts them towards making a competitive buying decision, for what to buy and what not to buy. These practical nodes can be classified as external (communication & fragmentation of media, value based choice, cultural factors, time pressures, long-run purchases else) and internal factors (self-choice, friend advice, age or gender difference, comparison array, conflict of choice between heart & mind, information circle else) to form the opinion, attitude and belief of consumers for a particular brand or a product purchase.

Zablah, Franke, Brown, & Bartholomew (2012) - Point of reference/direction (Orientation) of almost every firm and institution is going to be customer-centric at the cost of earning every cent of profits. The author(s) think that customer-centricity is an embedded psychological and behavioral attribute, of an individual preference; It also ensures compatibility of expectations of value sharing, between two-way interaction of firm's employee and customer (certainly, both have their own exchange difference), but an agent of customer orientation resolves whole issue.

Chizzoli & Pace (2012) - A competitive communication message involves that customer is not the receiver of a product but of the final value of competencies of the firm's output, and that builds consumer trust, eventually we say that the brand equity (added worth) of a product; it all depends on content of the advertising that stands to make stronger in a sense of creating competency of perceived promotion, behavioral & psychological effect. Further, it is

pointed out that somewhat advertising is difficult to convey company competency, as it is a one-way communication process.

Almeidaa, Abreua, Reisa, & Cardoso (2013) - Division of media channels and audience choice has been found as the key determinants of interactive advertising success. It is to ponder on advertising time, channel selection, placement geography and content that tend to be proved as control factors of interactive learning. The research concludes that primary consideration of firms resources, relates to the investment of advertising cost, while at the secondary level, it tries to capture consumer attention on the advertising way.

Bouazza (2013) - Involvement of marketers is increasing as a rate of a multiplier factor to the customer awareness; A comparison has been made in their research between brand-orientation sponsorship (which tends to produce substantial profits for brand and firm) and a public-orientation sponsorship (which tends to spend cost of earnings to support public). It is a qualitative research and finally suggests that consumer awareness to the sponsorship is just no more than the company earnings approach, with no kind of proper public interest in it.

S. Busena & Mustaffa (2014) - Advertising has been a root cause of developing the brand equity for its long run perspectives and sales results; as it a complete set of turning one's mind around the situation of purchase intentions. There is a huge gap in between placing the interactive advertisements on the online media in the marketing discussions for a variety of worldwide markets, like the less developed nations, where the cost of media campaign is higher and the sales in return are lower than the forecasted model.

Adhikary (2014) - Advertising plays a significant role in second step (that is searching information) from a viewpoint of five step consumer purchasing model. It furnishes consumer mind with learning and experience of what is available in market for his/her need intentions. The author(s) describes that higher advertising extension in a product array within industry, proposes high battle of competition among the advertiser(s) to capture consumer purchase intentions; the need is to focus consumer habit (perceived promotion) and nature (psychology) of buying decisions. Further, he points out that previous consumer knowledge also helps them to build mental associations for brands in excellence as per their committed experience, renowned advice or product support services.

Soomro, Goraya, Saba, & Ansari (2014) - Introducing a new Personal Care Product development (in Khairpur), suggests that Voice of customer, enables the organizations to identify for possible improvement in on-going product; if possible, find out the need of a new product variety or completely a new product itself; It would increase the consumer retention base for personal care products.

Muneer, Javed, Khan, & Long (2014) - Organizations have been trying to build the perceived organization support (Perceived Promotion) and organizational trust, in the eyes of customers as well as employees, so that commitment timeline for the audience may be generated in order to prescribe an influential dimension of knowledge-sharing behavior by both (customer and employee) in their surroundings for organizational image promotion and development.

Kavoura (2014) - Based on the facts of making a place as a brand for the visitors, is a chapter to be thoroughly studied in the subjects of national policies for its strategic outcomes; Such an advertising should emphasize on characteristics of psychological, social and demographic features to be explained in its promotion, in order to better understand about ones civilizations, traditions, myths and life sciences.

Sridevia (2014) - Competing array of involving the famous personalities in advertising campaigns enables the firms to renovate in a sense to build the credibility of advertisements, as the celebrities have more influencing authority in general public, especially for personal care products at all. Every brand is commercialized to initially involve the audience and then to persuade them for buying intentions and this is what can be achieved simpler by endorsing the brands of excellence via celebrity advertising.

Salceanu (2014) - Advertising management can be very difficult for the companies as per the personality difference in between individuals residing in same sample and class; it is what the research call as market dynamics of consumer behavior, whereby the personality factors can oppose the communication message to the individuals, as part of their no preferring choice. Successful advertisers need to focus on identification of manipulating factors, in perspectives of human acceptance of a commercialized message.

Kakkosa, Trivellasb, & Sdroliasc (2015) - The consumers are influenced to make purchases based on how much (quantitatively) they know about a brand, what is its perceived benefit and cost (value analysis), how much excellence does it have for its attributes (quality), how it relates to consumers (demographics) and finally how much it costs. If all the questions are working to answer positively, the consumer purchase intentions are formed to buy a product for their need. The study is limited to geographic array of Greek customers.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

To scrutinize considered variable(s) for building advertising competence for positive consumer purchase decisions.

4. PROPOSED RESEARCH MODEL

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

- H1: Orientation/Consciousness has a significant impact on Consumer Purchase Decisions.*
- H2: The Creativity/Innovation has a significant impact on Consumer Purchase Decisions.*
- H3: Differentiation has a significant impact on Consumer Purchase Decisions.*
- H4: Cost Criteria has No significant impact on Consumer Purchase Decisions.*
- H5: The extension of perceived promotion has a significant impact on Consumer Purchase Decisions.*
- H6: Behaviors and Psychological Factors have a significant impact on Consumer Purchase Decisions.*

6. METHODOLOGY

6.1 Data Collection Method

Data was collected through primary source of information by generating set of questionnaires, containing 40 items; from those 3 items were for demographics (gender, age group and qualification) and remaining all other items were measured through close ended responses on five-point Likert scale (1: Strongly Disagree, 2: Disagree, 3: Neutral, 4: Agree, 5: Strongly Agree). Secondary data was also collected through different publications, for quoting the work of other authors related to our study.

6.2 Sampling Method

Random sampling method was used, while collecting the data and 209 respondents were approached for the responses.

6.3 Quantitative Technique

- Step-1: At first instance reliability of instrument was checked through SPSS-18.*
- Step-2: Data reduction method was used to form the factors from different variables.*
- Step-3: Linear Regression was applied to check the inter-relationship between independent and dependent variable(s).*

6.4 Diagnostic Test

$$CPD = \alpha + OC\beta_1 + D\beta_2 + CI\beta_3 + CC\beta_4 + PP\beta_5 + BPI\beta_6 + \mu$$

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

7.1 Reliability Analysis

Table - 1	
Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
0.892	37

The study instrument is quite reliable with the value of Cronbach's alpha, which is about 0.892 for 37 items included in the questionnaire. (Table-1)

7.2 Factor Analysis

Table - 2

Items	Factors						
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
	OC	D	CI	CC	PP	BPI	CPD
OC3	0.465						
OC4	0.466						
OC5	0.392						
OC6	0.342						
OC8	0.388						
D1		0.502					
D2		0.503					
D3		0.500					
CI1			0.463				
CI2			0.501				
CI3			0.499				
CI4			0.481				
CC1				0.440			
CC2				0.703			
CC3				0.684			
PP1					0.465		
PP3					0.522		
PP4					0.406		
PP7					0.384		
BPI1						0.392	
BPI2						0.635	
BPI3						0.451	
BPI4						0.446	
CPD1							0.398
CPD2							0.305
CPD3							0.350
CPD4							0.363
CPD5							0.412
CPD6							0.376

Exploratory factor analysis method is used for reduction of data and summing up the same into concluding factors; where F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, F6 represents the independent variable(s) and F7 represents dependent variable. While the OC, D, CI, CC, PP, BPI and CPD (Table-2) refers to initial key letters to the inclined variables as per their names mentioned in research model. The point here to be noted is the excluding of those cross loading items of questionnaire in data reduction for significant factors generation, which were having coefficient absolute value below 0.30.

7.3 Model & Results Discussion

Table - 3

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.730	0.533	0.526	0.688

Table - 4

ANOVA						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	110.846	3	36.949	77.964	0.000
	Residual	97.154	205	0.474	-----	-----
	Total	208.000	208	-----	-----	-----

The Adjusted R² refers to overall fitness of the model and the rest is error term; in this case the value of Adjusted R² is about 0.526 (Table-3) that is approximately 53% contribution of influential level of three independent variables (OC, PP & BPI) to the dependent variable, while the rest of three variables (D, CI & CC) have been kept out of consideration in regression results generation for their insignificant level. Which ultimately suggests that the error term is about 47% but the inclusive model is fit at the significance level of 0.000 (Table-4)

Table - 5

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.827E-17	0.048	-----	0.000	1.000
	Orientation/Consciousness	0.216	0.060	0.216	3.617	.000
	Perceived Promotion	0.342	0.063	0.342	5.390	.000
	Behavioral & Psychological issues	0.316	0.059	0.316	5.333	.000

The beta (*Table-5*) suggests that there exists a direct relationship among three independent variables (OC, PP & BPI) and dependent variable (CPD), whereby OC, PP and BPI has a beta value of 0.216, 0.342 and 0.316 respectively excluding the insignificant variables; which represents no strong relationship among the proposed variables as per their beta value.

8. CONCLUSION

The prime objective of the study was to scrutinize considered variables as per the proposed research model, for building advertising competence for positive consumer purchase decisions in personal care products industry. Thanks to the versatility of the research that we have screened out three contributing variables in building the advertising competence by boosting the core dimensions of *orientation/consciousness* in media advertising campaign, considering the *facts and opinions (perceived promotion)* of consumers about the personal care products and involving the *behavioral and psychological impacting factors* of prospects in order to capture the value in return in the considered market, while the rest can be neglected to avoid the resources wastage and promote efficiency.

The Hypothesis H1, H4, H5 & H6 being formed, held true for the mentioned study and they are accepted, while H2 & H3 stay untrue and can be rejected for the same in achieving the advertising competence.

9. LIMITATIONS

The study is limited in a sense of resources and time being spent as per the course work requirement, neglecting the *socioeconomic status* of participating individuals in specifying the *geographic boundaries* of a rural city of Khairpur Mirs, Sindh, Pakistan and *product industry of personal care* in advertising competence.

1.0. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The study reveals the gap of 47% as per the intimation of error term that suggests for the prospecting researchers to consider the remaining factors being not considered here in this study, like socioeconomic status, individual differences, presentation or adoption of personal care product and other(s).

LIST OF REFERENCES

Acquisti, A., & Spiekermann, S. (2011). Do Interruptions Pay off? Effects of Interruptive Ads on Consumers' Willingness to Pay. *Journal of Interactive Marketing* , 25 (04), 226–240.

Adhikary, A. (2014). Advertising: A Fusion Process between Consumer and Product. *Procedia Economics and Finance* , 11, 230 – 238.

Almeidaa, P., Abreua, J., Reisa, M., & Cardoso, B. (2013). Interactive trends in the TV advertising landscape. *Procedia Technology* , 09, 399 – 404.

Bouazza, H. (2013). Comparing the consumers’ consciousness of the commercial sponsorship and the social cause sponsorship: A qualitative research. *Case Studies Journal ISSN (2305-509X)* , 02 (03).

Chizzoli, C., & Pace, S. (2012). Competence-Based Communication: Theoretical insights and empirical findings in the Initial Public Offering setting. *Viale Filippetti* , 9.

Goyal, A., & Kumar, S. (2012). Review of Various Functional Factors Which Affect Consumer’s Decision. *International Journal of Business and Management Economics Res* , 03 (01), 452-461.

- Haque, A., Rahman, S., Ahmed, I. S., Yasmin, F., & Asri, A. (2011). Assessing the impact of Advertisement towards Malay Consumers: an Empirical Study of Fast Food Restaurants in Malaysia. *Business Management Dynamics* , 01 (02), 39-53.
- Hemmatfar, M., Salehi, M., & Bayat, M. (2010). Competitive Advantages and Strategic Information Systems. *International Journal of Business and Management* , 05 (07).
- Kakkosa, N., Trivellasb, P., & Sdroliasc, L. (2015). Identifying Drivers of Purchase Intention for Private Label Brands. Preliminary Evidence from Greek Consumers. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* , 175, 522-528.
- Kavoura, A. (2014). A Conceptual Communication Model for Nation Branding in the Greek Framework. Implications for Strategic Advertising Policy. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* , 148, 32 – 39.
- Liu, S.-N., Lin, Y.-T., & Chen, Y.-C. (2011). Professional competencies for marketing managers in Taiwan: an application of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). *World Transactions on Engineering and Technology Education* , 09 (04).
- Muneer, S., Javed, S. M., Khan, S.-u.-r., & Long, C. S. (2014). An Incorporated Structure of Perceived Organizational Support, Knowledge-Sharing Behavior, Organizational Trust and Organizational Commitment: A Strategic Knowledge Management Approach. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences* , 08 (01), 42-57.
- Rajagopal, D. (2006, 01). Influence of Advertising Variability, Brand Extension Effects, Brand Name, Variety Seeking Behavior and Customer Value on Buying Decisions: A Multi-experiment Analysis. *RePEc (Research Papers in Economics)* .
- S. Busena, S. M., & Mustafa, C. S. (2014). The Role of Interactive Advertisements in Developing Consumer based Brand Equity: A Conceptual Discourse. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* , 155, 98-103.
- Salceanu, C. (2014). Personality factors and resistance to the manipulation of advertising. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* , 127, 5–9.
- Soomro, M. I., Goraya, N. A., Saba, K., & Ansari, B. F. (2014). Role of Voice of Customer in New Personal Care Product Development. *Case Studies Journal ISSN (2305-509X)* , 03 (06).
- Sridevia, D. J. (2014). Effectiveness of Celebrity Advertisement on Select FMCG – An Empirical Study. *Procedia Economics and Finance* , 11, 276 – 288.
- Zablah, A. R., Franke, G. R., Brown, T. J., & Bartholomew, D. E. (2012). How and When Does Customer Orientation Influence Frontline Employee Job Outcomes? A Meta-Analytic Evaluation. *Journal of Marketing; American Marketing Association.* , 76, 21-40.